

PERCEIVED INTERPARENTAL CONFLICT, EMOTIONAL REGULATION AND ATTITUDE TOWARDS MARRIAGE AMONG UNMARRIED PEOPLE

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Abstract

This study explores and investigated the relationship between perceived interparental conflict influences emotional regulation and attitudes toward marriage among unmarried young adults. Specifically, it examines the impact of childhood exposure to parental conflict on adult emotional coping mechanisms, and how these emotional regulation patterns affect perceptions of romantic relationships and marriage. The study also investigates the mediating role of emotional regulation in the link between interparental conflict and marital attitudes, such as expectations of stability, commitment, and emotional security. A correlational design was employed using a mixed-methods approach. The sample included 300 unmarried individuals (150 males and 150 females), aged 18–25, from two universities in Sialkot, Pakistan, all from middle socioeconomic backgrounds. Data were collected through self-report surveys measuring perceived interparental conflict, emotional regulation difficulties, and marital attitudes. Additionally, structured interviews were conducted with a subset of participants. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, Pearson correlation, one-way ANOVA, and linear regression. Results showed a significant positive correlation between perceived interparental conflict and emotional regulation difficulties. Higher levels of childhood conflict exposure were linked to greater emotional dysregulation in adulthood. Emotional regulation also mediated the relationship between interparental conflict and marital attitudes. Participants from high-conflict families expressed more negative or cautious views of marriage, including fear of commitment and skepticism about long-term relationships. Regression analyses confirmed that perceived conflict significantly predicted emotional regulation challenges and negative attitudes toward marriage.

In conclusion, early family dynamics profoundly influence adult emotional functioning and perceptions of romantic relationships. These findings highlight the importance of early interventions and counseling efforts targeting emotional skills in children from high-conflict homes. They also underscore the need for educational programs to support young adults in developing healthy relationship expectations. Limitations include reliance on self-report data and the study's

geographic focus. Future research should consider longitudinal designs and broader cultural samples to enhance generalizability.

INTRODUCTION

This study explores the relationship between perceived interparental conflict and emotion regulation, focusing on how these factors influence attitudes toward marriage among unmarried university students. Marriage, traditionally seen as a cornerstone of social and emotional stability, has evolved in perception, particularly among young adults. While some still see it as essential for companionship and growth, others view it as burdensome due to changing societal expectations (Amato, 2014).

Historically, marriage signified a lifelong emotional and social contract, often motivated by family, financial stability, or societal norms. Modern views emphasize emotional fulfillment, equality, and mutual growth (Garmendia, 2014). Healthy marriages are linked to physical and psychological well-being, emotional support, and improved life satisfaction (Waite & Gallagher, 2000). In contrast, marital dissatisfaction often stems from poor communication, infidelity, abuse, unrealistic expectations, and emotional disconnection (Gottman & Levenson, 2000). Global marriage customs vary widely. In Western countries, monogamy is predominant, often marked by vows and civil or religious ceremonies (Lenson, 2019). In polygyny, one man marries multiple women (common in parts of Africa and the Middle East), while polyandry involves one woman marrying several men, found in Himalayan regions (James, 2020). Same-gender marriages are legal in many Western countries but remain controversial elsewhere (Peter, 2017). Group marriages and marriages for legal or economic reasons also exist but are less common (Cunningham, 2016).

In Asia, Chinese and Korean marriages emphasize family values, traditional rituals, and respect for elders, though modern trends increasingly allow for love marriages (Chia-Hui, & Yun-Hee Park, 2001). In Pakistan, marriage is both a religious and cultural obligation, often arranged by families to uphold social norms. Marital satisfaction is more closely tied to fulfilling familial duties than individual happiness (Zaidi et al., 2012). Family systems theory posits that interrelated relationships within the family unit shape

child development (Cox & Paley, 2003). Conflict between parents—especially when expressed destructively through aggression, withdrawal, or hostility—can harm children’s emotional regulation and future relationships (Cummings, 2017). Children exposed to high-conflict marriages may struggle with stress, anxiety, and difficulty forming trusting relationships (Break, 2019).

University students in emerging adulthood are particularly influenced by their early family environments. Perceived interparental conflict can shape their emotional coping mechanisms and perceptions of marital stability and satisfaction. If conflicts were resolved constructively during childhood, students may carry healthier emotional regulation and optimistic views of marriage. Conversely, destructive conflict may breed mistrust, fear of commitment, and emotional detachment (Ary & Furnham, 2019).

The study underscores the critical influence of interparental conflict and emotional regulation on young adults' attitudes toward marriage. Encouraging healthy conflict resolution and emotional support within families can foster better emotional adjustment and healthier views of marriage in the next generation.

Rational of the Study

The aim of this study is to examine and evaluate the association between perceived interparental conflict and emotion regulation, and how these factors influence attitudes toward marriage among unmarried university students. The objective of this study is to explore the prevalence of perceived interparental conflict among university students. This study assesses the level of emotional regulation among individuals who have experienced interparental conflict. This research study aims to investigate the relationship between perceived interparental conflict and attitudes toward marriage. It also examines whether emotion regulation mediates the impact of interparental conflict on marriage attitudes. To provide insight into how early family experiences

influence future relationship expectations and emotional health.

Hypotheses

1. There will be a likely positive relationship between interparental conflict and attitude towards marriage among unmarried people’.
2. They will be likely to be a positive relationship between interparental conflict and emotion regulation.”

The main hypothesis of the present study is approved and the $P < .05$ which shows that interparental conflict that are significant relationship between attitude toward among unmarried people. These variables have significant relationship among who adult have faced the interparental conflicts there are prevailed different concept about the marriage among unmarried people. The "spillover hypothesis" suggests that conflict in the parental relationship may lead to negative parenting practices, affecting children's sense of security and emotional well-being (Davie & Cummings, 2006). Parental divorce and persistent disputes are associated with emotional instability and negative attitudes toward marriage in adulthood (Riggio, 2008). Studies also show that warm parenting can buffer externalizing symptoms in children, while over-control may increase internalizing issues (Benson & Gerard, 2006).

Research Methodology

Participants and Sampling

The target population consisted of unmarried individuals aged 19–25 years residing in Sialkot, Pakistan. Participants were selected from various private and public universities, as well as other local areas. Only individuals from middle to upper-middle socioeconomic classes with at least matriculation-level education were included. Divorced or widowed individuals and those from lower socioeconomic backgrounds were excluded. A total of 300 participants (150 male, 150 female) were selected using a convenience sampling method, which allows easy access to participants.

Research Design

A correlational research design was used to examine the relationship between interparental conflicts, emotion regulation (independent variables), and

attitudes toward marriage (dependent variable). This design identifies associations without manipulating variables (Paritha, 2009).

Inclusion/Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion

Inclusion criteria included from the ages of 19–25 in this research stud and also unmarried individuals (never married) included the survey data. Consent to participate before fill the survey questionnaire. Ability to understand and complete questionnaires.

Exclusion

Excluded the Individuals below 19 or above 25 from the survey data collection., Those unwilling or who did not provide informed consent and also Incomplete responses are not added the data collection. No experience of interparental conflict (where applicable)

Trust and Rapport

To build trust, the researcher introduced the study purpose, assured confidentiality, and offered clarification during questionnaire administration. Participants were informed they could access study details and withdraw at any point.

Measures

Demographic form collected data on age, gender, marital status, education, Perceived interparental conflicts emotion regulation and attitude toward marriage among in unmarried people.

Children’s Perception of Interparental Conflict Scale (CPIC)

A 39-item instrument assessing conflict properties, threat perception, and self-blame, using a 3-point Likert scale (Bickham & Fiese, 1997).

Emotion Regulation Questionnaire (ERQ)

A 10-item Likert scale (1–7) assessing cognitive reappraisal and expressive suppression (Gross, 2003).

General Attitudes toward Marriage Scale (GAMS)

A 10-item scale using a 7-point Likert response format assessing positive and negative views about marriage (Park & Rosén, 2013).

Intent to Marry Scale (IMS)

A 3-item subscale of the Marital Scales measuring future marital intentions

Overt Marital Conflict Scale

A 10-item scale measuring frequency of observed interparental conflicts (Porter & O’Leary, 1980).

Research Site and Procedure

The research procedures began with careful topic selection, considering relevance, feasibility, novelty, and ethical standards, under supervisor guidance. A focused and researchable question addressing a gap in literature or practical issue was identified. Feasibility was ensured by assessing available resources like time, databases, and participants. Appropriate research design and methods were chosen with supervisor approval to collect valid data. Permission letters were obtained from universities in Sialkot, and informed consent was taken from participants. Questionnaires were distributed in English, with Urdu explanations provided when needed, ensuring confidentiality and voluntary participation. After data collection, participants and institutional authorities were thanked for their cooperation.

Ethical Considerations

Participants were informed of the study’s purpose, their right to withdraw, and the confidentiality of

Results

Table 1: Frequencies and Percentage of the sociodemographics Characteristic information of the participants (N=300).

	N		%	Cumulative percent	
Gender					
Male	150				
Female	150				
Age	minimum	maximum		Mean age	
	18	25	45	22.70	100.0
Marital Status	300				
Unmarried					
Birth order	56	117	65		100.0
Education	90	207	186		100.0
BS					
M. A					

their responses. All psychological tools were ethically sourced, and informed consent was obtained. Data was used solely for research purposes.

Scoring and Statistical Analysis

Responses were scored using the respective test manuals. Data was entered into Microsoft Excel and analyzed via SPSS v12. Descriptive statistics were calculated, and ANOVA was used to examine gender differences in marital attitudes. Correlation analysis tested associations among variables. Linear regression explored predictive relationships between interparental conflict, emotion regulation, and marital attitudes.

Operational Definitions

Interparental Conflict

Disagreements or arguments between parents perceived by the child, measured using CPIC (Davies, 2002).

Emotion Regulation

The ability to manage and express emotional responses, measured using ERQ (Gross, 2002).

Attitude Toward Marriage (GAMS)

An individual’s perception and expectations about marriage and marital relationships (Willoughby, 2010).

Socioeconomic status				
Upper	274	26	71	100.0
Middle				
Residential Status				
Local	101	199	20	100.0

Table 1 the study involved 300 participants with a mix of birth orders—56% were second-born, while 65% were first or third-born. Educationally, 186 participants were undergraduates, 207 volunteered as undergraduates, and 90 were

graduates. Socioeconomic status showed 274 participants belonged to the middle class, and 26 to other categories. In terms of background, 200 were local residents, 109 were migrants, and 199 came from family business backgrounds.

Table 2: On the basis of gender differences a comparison on the variables Interparental conflicts emotions regulation and attitude towards marriage among unmarried people (N=300)

Variable	Male (n = 150)		Female (n = 150)		t	95%pCL			cohen sd
	M	SD	M	SD		P	LL	UL	
emotion regulation	52.84	10.47	52.67	10.05	146	.88	-2.159	2.506	.17
Intent marriage	10.51	3.65	9.93	3.46	1.369	.16	-.235	1.381	.16
Positive marriage	15.47	4.24	15.61	4.90	-.277	.78	-1.133	853	.30
Negative marriage	10.73	3.55	10.91	3.73	-.434	.66	-.960	613	.49
Marriage doubt	12.91	3.51	13.11	3.59	-.488	.62	-1.007	607	.57
Attitude marriage romance	12.33	3.52	12.22	3.78	.253	.80	-.724	938	.30
Attitude marriage respect	21.92	5.01	21.96	4.91	-.070	.94	-1.167	1.087	.80
Attitude marriage trust	21.79	4.52	22.24	4.97	-.823	.41	-1.537	630	.71
Attitude marriage finances	23.453	5.42	22.32	5.11	1.85	.06	-.0717	2.32	.21
Attitude marriage meaning	16.59	4.56	16.29	4.30	.586	.55	-.708	1.308	.67
Attitude marriage physical intimacy	12.24	3.50	12.10	3.19	.362	.71	-.622	902	.41
Interperntal conflicts	80.94	8.57	82.46	8.120	-1.57	.11	-3.41	377	.80

Table 2 shows no significant gender difference in emotion regulation (M = 52.84, SD = 10.47 for males; M = 52.67, SD = 10.05 for females; t = .146, p = .884). However, significant differences were observed in

emotion regulation, attitude toward marriage, and interparental conflict (t = -3.77, 10.42; p = .000) between male and female university students.

Table .3: Summary of Linear Regression Interparetnal conflicts emotion regulation attitude toward marriage among unmarried people in university students (N= 300).

Predictor	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	F	DF	P
Interparental conflicts	.302	.091	.056	2.62	11	.003

*p< .05

In the table no 4, the findings of the currant study study have shown interparental conflict is a strong predictor of emotion regulation and attitude toward marriage among unmarried people in university

students,with he p<.05 which is .003. with the R is .302, R²'is .091, Adjusted R² is equal to .056,while F is 2.622 and p value is .003.

Table 4

Model	Sum of squire	df	Mean squire	f	sig
Regression	1907.080	11	173.371	2.622	.003
Residual	19039.920	288	166.111		
Total	20947	299			

independent variable; Interparental conflicts

Dependent variables; emotion regulation and attitude marriage toward unmarried people

Discussion

This study aimed to explore the relationship between perceived interparental conflict, emotional regulation, and attitudes toward marriage among unmarried adults in Pakistan. The findings reveal significant correlations between these variables, suggesting that early familial experiences, particularly those involving conflict between parents, can have long-lasting effects on young adults' emotional development and interpersonal beliefs. Consistent with past research, the study supports the notion that exposure to interparental conflict is significantly associated with emotion regulation difficulties (El-Sheikh, 2004). Many adults reported high scores in both perceived interparental conflict and emotional dysregulation, indicating that unresolved or hostile parental interactions during childhood may model maladaptive emotional coping mechanisms. Children who witness conflict may internalize aggressive, avoidant, or suppressive strategies that persist into adulthood, manifesting as emotional instability, trust issues, and relationship insecurities (Grych et al., 2004).

Interestingly, while previous studies suggest that both mother and father attachments moderate this relationship, the current study found that only sibling attachment avoidance played a significant moderating role. This highlights the potential influence of sibling dynamics in emotionally buffering or amplifying the

effects of parental discord (Doherty & Feeney, 2004).The second hypothesis, predicting a positive relationship between interparental conflict and attitudes toward marriage, was also supported. Participants who experienced higher levels of conflict between parents were more likely to develop negative or ambivalent attitudes toward marriage. This aligns with research suggesting that children of high-conflict homes often fear repeating their parents' dysfunctional patterns, which can lead to a lack of confidence in romantic relationships and hesitation toward commitment (Amato & Booth, 1991). Some, however, may idealize marriage as a corrective experience, striving to build healthier relationships than those they observed growing up (Cunningham & Thornton, 2006).

Cultural factors further complicate these dynamics. In Pakistan, family structures are typically collectivist, emphasizing emotional suppression, harmony, and family reputation. These cultural expectations may contribute to the underreporting or internalization of emotional distress resulting from interparental conflict (Bootal, 2011). As such, many individuals may struggle silently with the psychological toll of familial discord, unable to express or process emotions in a healthy way. From a theoretical perspective, this study reinforces the emotional security hypothesis, which posits that children's emotional well-being is deeply influenced by the

security of familial relationships (Davies et al., 2002). Practically, the findings emphasize the importance of fostering emotional resilience and healthy coping strategies in children, particularly those from conflict-prone households. Early intervention programs that teach emotional regulation and relationship skills may mitigate the adverse effects of interparental conflict. In conclusion, this research highlights the enduring influence of parental relationships on young adults' emotional functioning and views on marriage. While interparental conflict can negatively shape attitudes and emotional regulation, individual resilience and external support systems, such as siblings or community resources, may serve as protective factors. Future studies should include larger, more diverse samples and consider cultural and linguistic variations to better understand these relationships across different societal contexts. Therapeutic interventions that address family communication, emotional awareness, and attachment could help reduce the intergenerational transmission of relational dysfunction and promote healthier romantic expectations in young adults.

H2

'There will be a likely positive relationship between interparental conflict and attitude towards marriage among unmarried people'.

The 2nd hypothesis of the present study is approved and the $P < .05$ which shows that interparental conflict that are significant relationship between attitude toward among unmarried people. These variables have significant relationship among who adult have faced the interparental conflicts there are prevailed different concept about the marriage among unmarried people.

Several studies suggest that individuals from high conflict families may develop negative attitudes toward marriage, fearing that their own relationships will mirror their parents troubled dynamics. The studies found that children exposed to frequent parental conflicts often developed lower confidence in their ability to maintain healthy romantic relationships, leading to pessimism about marriage (Amato & Booth, 1991). Researches showed that individuals from high conflict families tend to report lower expectations of marital stability and higher fear of commitment (Stanley & Markman,

2008). The studies provided evidence that parental conflict and divorce can diminish children's belief in the institution of marriage, making them more likely to delay marriage or reject it entirely (Kapinus, 2004).

The present study the participants who witnessed interparental conflict but may difficulties to developed a strong emotional regulation skills demonstrated and resilient outlook on romantic relationships. This suggests that while exposure to conflict in the parental home can shape perceptions, it does necessarily lead to negative views of marriage. Instead, individuals with adaptive emotional regulation are capable of learning from past family dynamics, using them to build healthier expectations for their future relationships. This outcome highlights the adaptive potential of emotional regulation as a mediating factor that can buffer the adverse effects of early relational stress. Rather than uniformly deterring belief in the institution of marriage, exposure to conflict may, in some cases, foster critical reflection, emotional growth, and a greater appreciation for healthy relational dynamics—especially when emotional coping mechanisms are strong.

Limitation & Recommendation

It was very difficult to access the scales. It took almost a month to get it done from the author permission. Because Sialkot University students were included in the study, it is challenging to say that the findings apply to the broader population. It's possible that this study only applies to undergraduate students in other cities. Encourage premarital counseling programs to explore clients' family-of-origin experiences, especially interparental conflict, as these can shape attitudes and expectations toward marriage and intimate relationships. Future studies should adopt longitudinal designs to better understand how exposure to interparental conflict affects emotional regulation and marital attitudes over time, allowing for better insight into causal relationships.

Conclusion

This study explored the complex interplay between perceived interparental conflict, emotional regulation, and attitudes toward marriage among unmarried individuals. The sample of the study was adult. This study brings indication that these three

variables have relationship. There was significant positive correlation between interparental conflict and difficulty in emotional regulation while interparental conflict and attitude towards marriage have significant correlation. It indicated that the higher interparental conflict there is difficult to manage in emotion regulation in adult and also had a concept about the marriage either positive mindset or negative concept about marriage.

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